
A STUDY OF THE AWARENESS ABOUT THE USE OF WHATSAPP IN TEACHING AMONG STUDENT TEACHER

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INTRODUCTION

The use of social media has become essential in Education and Teaching learning Process. The use of social media specifically in the field of community and Educational development has also recently begun to receive intellectual attention. There is strong facts to suggest that social networks can improve Teaching Learning Process. The prospective to transform the methods of dialoging, information sharing, and relationship building in the Educational community in the twenty first century. WhatsApp also introduces the use of various technological tools and methods for sharing and discussing information. An instant messaging system for smartphones from WhatsApp . Founded in 2009 by Brian Acton and Jan Koum and running on all major smartphone platforms, WhatsApp uses the Internet as an alternative to the SMS text messaging system. Via Wi-Fi, phone subscribers pay nothing for WhatsApp messages. However, even if they use their cellular data plans for WhatsApp messages, text messages comprise only a handful of bytes, and thousands can be sent for a minuscule fraction of their total data usage.

WhatsApp is an opportunity to share or distribute information to every common Student and Teacher, where they have an opportunity to create and share their views and thoughts. If compared, WhatsApp helps one connect and interact with others. For example, student and teacher can upload, share, and view videos and text messages. WhatsApp are an excellent option for individuals who wish to gain information, collaborate and share ideas on various social media content, and for the individuals who would like to have more information about the world around them.

The use of WhatsApp is essential as an educational development tool in terms of building and improving communications, documenting development efforts, sharing information in real time, and informing and reaching a wider audience than was possible at any time in history. Perhaps more importantly, WhatsApp can give a chance to those who have the skills and abilities to use new technologies by helping them, social media and WhatsApp can enhance the educational capacity of education community members.

Statement of The Problem :

A study of the awareness about The Use of WhatsApp in Teaching among Student Teacher.

Definition of a WhatsApp

WhatsApp Messenger is a cross-platform instant messaging application available only to the smart phones: iPhone, BlackBerry, Android and Symbian. In addition to normal texting, WhatsApp Messenger users can send each other images, video and audio media messages, as well as engage in group conversations between multiple users.

Objectives :

(1) To compare the awareness about The Use of WhatsApp in Teaching among Science graduate and other than science graduate Student Teacher.

(2) To compare the awareness about The Use of WhatsApp in Teaching among Rural graduate and urban graduate Student Teacher.

Hypothesis:-

- 1) There is no significant difference between the awareness about The Use of WhatsApp in Teaching among Science graduate and other than science graduate Student Teacher.
- 2) There is no significant difference between the awareness about The Use of WhatsApp in Teaching among rural area student and urban Student Teacher .

Population:

In the present study B.Ed. students Teacher of PVDT College of Education for Women have been selected.

Sample :

The research selected PVDT college of Educations' Student Teacher(year 2012-2013) as a sample with present study 80 students have been selected with the help of purposive sample method.

Limitations of The Study :

- (1) In this study, only PVDT college of Education Marathi Medium student have been selected .

Tool of Study :

“awareness Questionnaire” has been developed by researcher for the present study to know about the awareness about The Use of WhatsApp in Teaching among Student Teacher.

Research Methodology :

Survey method was used for the present study.

Procedure :

Awareness Questionnaire was administered on Student Teacher.

Statistical Analysis :

The data was analyzed by using the basis of table given below:-

Table
Difference in Mean Score of Student Teacher Awareness
About The Use of WhatsApp

Sr. No.	Group	Sample	Mean	SD	df	't' Score	Level Of Significant
01	Rural graduate	31	73.85	10.53	78	0.559	No Significance
	Urban graduate	49	75.26	6.88			
02	Science graduate	46	76.54	8.73	78	1.94	No Significance
	Other than science graduate	34	78	6.96			

Interpretation:

As per the study of student teacher awareness of The Use of WhatsApp in Teaching among Student Teacher. Rural and urban ,Science Faculty and other than science faculty are value of 't' in the table is less than the value of 't' in the table 'd'. Therefore, the null hypothesis is not significant at the level of 0.05. The null hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion

As for as the of difference between Rural and urban, Science Faculty and other than science faculty student teacher awareness of The Use of WhatsApp in Teaching among Student are concerned value of 't' in the table is less than the value of 't' in the table 'D' The null hypothesis is accepted at the level of 0.05

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